

Thiazolines: Part II.
Synthesis of 3- β -Aryloxyethyl-2- β -Aryloxyethyl-Imino-4-Aryl- Δ^4 -
Thiazoline Hydrohalides

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25 Thiazolines have been synthesised as potential antimicrobials by condensation of Sym. thioureas with phenacyl halides.

Eisman^{1,2} *et al.* found that thiazolines were more active than the corresponding Sym. thioureas from which they were prepared. The Sym. β -aryloxyethyl thioureas which we had earlier synthesised showed some potency as antimicrobials³. It was thought of interest to cyclise them to the corresponding thiazolines. 3- β -Aryloxyethyl-2- β -aryloxyethyl-imino-4-aryl- Δ^4 -thiazoline hydrohalides have been prepared by condensation of 1,3-bis-(β -aryloxyethyl)-2-thioureas with phenacyl halides. These thiazolines have some resemblance with tuberculostatic thiazolines prepared by Mizzoni⁴.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The required 1,3-bis-(β -aryloxyethyl)-2-thioureas were prepared from β -aryloxyethylamines as described earlier³. The new isothiocyanate and Sym. thiourea prepared in the course of this work are β -(3,4-dimethyl-phenoxy)ethyl isothiocyanate, b.p. 120°/3 mm. (Found : S, 15.5. C₁₁H₁₃NOS requires S, 15.4%) and 1,3-bis-(β -3,4-dimethylphenoxyethyl)-2-thiourea, m.p. 118°. (Found : S, 8.7. C₂₁H₂₈N₂O₂S requires S, 8.6%).

3- β -Aryloxyethyl-2- β -aryloxyethyl-imino-4-aryl- Δ^4 -thiazoline hydrohalides : These were prepared from the corresponding thioureas and phenacyl halides as described earlier⁵

Compounds prepared are shown in Table 1.

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TABLE I

3- β -Aryloxyethyl-2- β -aryloxyethyl-imino-4-aryl- Δ^4 -thiazoline hydrohalides^a :

Sr. No.	R	R ₁	M.P. ^b °C	% Sulphur	
				Found	Calcd.
1	H	H	138-39	6.5	6.4
2	4-Chloro	H	161	5.5	5.7
3	2-Methyl	H	142	6.1	6.1
4	4-Methyl	H	154	6.2	6.1
5	2,4-Dimethyl	H	157	5.6	5.8
6	3,4-Dimethyl	H	160-61	5.9	5.8
7	2,4-Dichloro	H	155	5.0	5.0
8	2-Methyl-4-Chloro	H	107	5.3	5.4
9	H	Cl	173	6.1	6.0
10	2-Chloro	Cl	148	5.4	5.3
11	4-Chloro	Cl	194-95	5.2	5.3
12	2-Methyl	Cl	107	5.6	5.7
13	4-Methyl	Cl	170	5.5	5.7
14	2,4-Dimethyl	Cl	174	5.3	5.4
15	3,4-Dimethyl	Cl	165	5.4	5.4
16	2-Methyl-4-Chloro	Cl	115	5.0	5.1
17	2-Chloro	H	140	6.5	6.1
18	H	OCH ₃	154	6.4	6.6
19	2-Chloro	OCH ₃	138-39	5.6	5.8
20	4-Chloro	OCH ₃	213	5.5	5.8
21	2-Methyl	OCH ₃	124	6.4	6.3
22	4-Methyl	OCH ₃	153-54	6.2	6.3
23	2,4-Dimethyl	OCH ₃	111	5.6	5.9
24	3,4-Dimethyl	OCH ₃	223	5.7	5.9
25	2-Methyl-4-Chloro	OCH ₃	85	5.2	5.5

a : Compds. 1-16 are hydrobromides and the rest are hydrochlorides.

b : All melting-points are uncorrected.

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